

Studies of Amino-acyl Insertion

A. B. Sen and M. S. Yajnik

Amino-acyl insertion reactions have been carried out with β -amino-acid ester of α -, β -, and γ -hydroxy-acid amides.

The amino-acyl insertion reaction is a special feature of the chemistry of polyamides. It has a bearing on the synthesis, isomerisation, and possibly degradation of peptide chain¹. Serine, threonine and cysteine occupy a unique position among common α -amino-acids. This is due to the fact that the general structure (I) allows for a peculiar rearrangement, when present in the peptide materials; amide of the structure (II) may function as alcohol or thiol in the esterification reaction with common amino-acids. The resulting ester (III) can rearrange in such way that XH is regenerated, the amino-acid residue is detached from X, and is inserted into the amide group CONH- of the material (III).

Amino-acyl insertion is therefore possible in a variety of compounds of general structure (V), the product of the rearrangement having the general structure (VI).

1. Brenner, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1957, 40, 1394.

The present work was therefore undertaken to study the amino-acyl insertion reaction with β -amino-acid esters of α -, β -, and γ -hydroxy-acid amides of types (VII), (VIII), and (IX).

(VII)

(VIII)

(IX)

The hydroxy-acid amides studied were salicylamide, *m*-hydroxybenzamide, lactamide, and mandelamide. The amino-acids used were β -aminobutyric acid, β -amino- β -phenylpropionic acid, and glycine. The amino-acid esters of hydroxyamides were prepared by the action of the amino-acid anhydride on the hydroxyamides in presence of HCl in ethyl acetate (Moore³). The esters, thus obtained, were then rearranged with sodium *t*-butoxide in *t*-butanol solution at 20° (Brenner¹). The anhydrides of β -amino-acids were prepared by the method of Leuches².

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethoxycarbonyl Derivatives of Amino-acids.—These were prepared by the following method according to Leuches².

The β -amino-acid (0.1 *M*) was dissolved in water (150 ml) containing NaOH (0.3 *M*). The solution was stirred mechanically at 0°, ethyl chloroformate (0.2 *M*) was added during 5 to 10 min., and stirring continued during 1/2 to 1 hour. The reaction mixture was made acidic to Congo red with HCl (conc.). Although ethoxycarbonyl derivatives of the higher amino-acids separated at this stage, but those of the lower amino-acids remained soluble in water. In the latter case, the solution was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure and the residue was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried over sodium sulphate and the extract evaporated under reduced pressure. The yields, m.p., and analyses of these compounds are recorded in Table I.

2. *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 857.

3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 2884.

TABLE I
 EtOOCNHR.

R.	M.P.	% Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
$\begin{array}{c} \text{—CH—CH}_2(\text{COOH}) \\ \\ \text{Me} \end{array}$	63°	85	C ₇ H ₁₃ O ₄ N	7.95	8.00
$\begin{array}{c} \text{—CH—CH}_2(\text{COOH}) \\ \\ \text{Ph} \end{array}$	80°	78	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ O ₄ N	5.84	5.90

N-Carboxy-acid Anhydrides of Amino-acids.—These anhydrides were prepared by following the methods of Leuches².

Ethoxycarbonyl derivative of the β -amino-acid (0.1*M*) and thionyl chloride (0.2 ml) were mixed together under cooling and the mixture was gently heated at 40° until the evolution of gas had ceased. The mixture was heated to 50-60° for 30 min. to complete the reaction. The excess of thionyl chloride was removed under reduced pressure and the crude residue was triturated with light petroleum (40-60°) till the solid anhydride separated. It was recrystallised from acetic anhydride. The yield, m.p., and analyses of the anhydrides are shown in Table II. The anhydride of glycine was prepared by the method of Leuches².

TABLE II

R.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.
Me	100°	60%	C ₅ H ₇ O ₃ N
Ph	98°	61%	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₃ N

Ester Hydrochlorides of Hydroxy-amides.—The general method of preparation (Moore³) is given below. HCl gas was passed in dry ethyl acetate (100 ml) till the increase in weight was 4g. To this was added the amide of the hydroxy-acid (0.1*M*) and *N*-carboxy-acid anhydride (0.1*M*). The mixture was then heated to 60° for 3 hours and the solution was left overnight. The ethyl acetate was decanted and the solution was taken in ethanol. The solution was evaporated to dryness; the residue was redissolved in ethanol and precipitated by ether, when the ester hydrochloride of the amino-acid was precipitated. The precipitate was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol-ether mixture. The m.p.s, yields, and analyses of these esters are reported in Table III.

TABLE III
 R-COO-R'.

R.	R'.	M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
	CH ₂ NH ₂ .HCl	60°	35	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	11.30	11.40
Do		130°	40	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	8.25	8.30
Do	-CH ₂ -NH ₂ .HCl	100°	52	C ₉ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	12.00	12.10
	-CH ₂ -CH-NH ₂ .HCl Ph	100°	43	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	8.63	8.70
Do	-CH ₂ -CH-NH ₂ .HCl Me	70°	58	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	10.74	10.80
	-CH ₂ -CH-NH ₂ .HCl Me	125°	55	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	10.68	10.80
Do	-CH ₂ -CH-NH ₂ .HCl Ph	135°	30	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	8.68	8.70
	-CH ₂ -NH ₂ .HCl	120°	38	C ₃ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	14.94	15.00

Amino-acyl Insertion

The insertion reactions were carried out by the procedure of Brenner¹, resulting in the formation of peptides. Amino-acid ester hydrochloride (90 mg.) was suspended at 20° in *t*-butanol (1.1g. potassium *t*-butoxide in 20 ml *t*-butanol). The mixture was shaken vigorously for 1 hour and then a mixture of Amberlite I RA-120(H) form (1.5 g.) and Amberlite IR-400 (OH) form (1g.) was added with water (25 ml) to maintain the pH at 6-7. It was filtered and *t*-butanol was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was then taken up in ethanol and the peptide precipitated with ether. It was recrystallised from methanol-ether mixture. The m.p.s, analyses, and yields of these compounds are recorded in Table IV.

 TABLE IV
 R-CO-NHR'.

R.	R'.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
	CH ₂ .CONH ₂	200°	80%	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₂	13.0	13.0
Do	-CH-CH ₂ .CONH ₂ Ph	109°	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₂	9.1	9.2
Do	>CH ₂ .CONH ₂	124°	67	C ₉ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₂	13.9	14.0

TABLE IV (contd.)

• R.	R ₁ .	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Nitrogen	
					Found.	Reqd.
	$\begin{array}{c} \text{Ph} \\ \\ -\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CONH}_2 \end{array}$	142°	72	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃	10.0	9.9
Do	$\begin{array}{c} -\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CONH}_2 \\ \\ \text{Me} \end{array}$	120°	68	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃	11.8	12.0
	$\begin{array}{c} -\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CONH}_2 \\ \\ \text{Me} \end{array}$	100°	71	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃	12.0	12.1
Do	$\begin{array}{c} -\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CONH}_2 \\ \\ \text{Ph} \end{array}$	75	78	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₃	9.9	9.9
$\begin{array}{c} \text{H} \\ \\ \text{CH}_3-\text{C}- \\ \\ \text{OH} \end{array}$	$-\text{CH}_2-\text{CONH}_2$	300°	65	C ₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃	19.0	19.0

One of the authors (M.S.Y.) wishes to thank the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for the award of a junior fellowship.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW.

Received January 20, 1964.